

EBFMC25-OP-79 · Karyotype Results of Patients with a History of Habitual Abortion in Ordu Province

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Habitual abortion, also referred to as recurrent pregnancy loss (RPL), is defined as the occurrence of two or more consecutive pregnancy losses before the 20th week of gestation (Practice Committee of ASRM, 2012). The estimated prevalence of habitual abortion is about 1–2% of all couples trying to conceive (Ford & Schust, 2009). It represents a significant emotional and medical challenge for affected individuals and often requires a multidisciplinary diagnostic and therapeutic approach. The most common causes of RPL are genetic abnormalities, anatomical uterine abnormalities, endocrine disorders, thrombophilic conditions, and immunological factor. In the general population, the prevalence of balanced chromosomal translocations is estimated to be about 0.2–0.3% (Braekeleer & Dao, 1990). However, in couples with habitual abortion, this rate increases significantly, ranging from 4% to 8%, depending on the population and diagnostic methods used (Franssen et al., 2005; Stirrat, 1990). A roughly 20- to 40-fold increase in the rate of chromosomal abnormalities makes peripheral blood karyotype analysis the first-line test in patients with habitual abortion.

Materials and Methods: A total of 242 patients who presented to the medical genetics outpatient clinic due to habitual abortion were evaluated. Pedigrees were drawn, and detailed pregnancy histories were recorded. Peripheral blood samples were obtained from all patients using heparinized tubes. The collected samples were referred to a contracted laboratory for lymphocyte culture (72-hour long-term culture) and subsequent chromosomal analysis. Metaphase spreads were prepared and stained with Giemsa, and karyotypes were generated at a resolution of 450–550 bands. All karyotypes were digitized and systematically analyzed. Cytogenetic results were interpreted and reported in accordance with the International System for Human Cytogenomic Nomenclature (ISCN 2021) guidelines.

Results: Among the 242 patients (121 females and 121 males), chromosomal abnormalities explaining the clinical findings were identified in 6 individuals (2.5%) (Table 1).

Table 1

Patient	Karyotype
1	46,XY,t(2;7)(q31;q21.2)
2	46,XY,t(3;17)(q22;q23)
3	46,XY,t(8;14)(q13;q24)
4	46,XY,t(1;5)(p12;p12)
5	46,XX,t(9;12)(p24;q22)
6	46,XY,t(3;5)(p23;p15.33)

All detected anomalies were balanced chromosomal translocations. Of the affected individuals, 5 were male and 1 was female.

Conclusion: Recurrent pregnancy loss is a common complication of gestation, affecting approximately 2% of couples attempting to conceive. An increased risk of chromosomal abnormalities has been reported in this patient group. Consistent with the literature, our study identified chromosomal anomalies in 2.5% of cases.

To our knowledge, this is the first study in our region investigating the relationship between habitual abortion and chromosomal abnormalities.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Habitual abortion, chromosomal translocation, karyotype, medical genetic

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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